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SIMPLE HOME-LAB EXPERIMENTS WITH DIGITAL DISCUSSIONS - AND THE WORLD OF PHYSICS BEHIND

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ABSTRACT

During the Covid-19 pandemic home-lab experiments were suggested to substitute for closed laboratories and experimental classes. Based on a competition among students in the 2nd semester of the Bachelor of Physics to determine the mass of a fly with home-lab experiments we present the approach of the winner experiment that allows to explore a broad range of physics touching the fields of mechanics, electronics, thermodynamics and statistics. The winner team chose an approach to measure the time that an empty sphere which has nearly the density of liquid water, needs to overcome a fixed distance in a water filled cylindrical tube under gravity. The approach allows for an analytical solution of the problem which can be proven and measured with high accuracy. The small effect of the weight change of the sphere by adding the mass of a fly (0.1 %) is nicely transferred to a macroscopic change of the time needed to sink down to the ground. Further improvements of the experiments are suggested by using different liquids, electronic timers or photosensors for more accurate measurements of time. An interesting approach works with a gradient of the sugar concentration in a cylindrical tube that results in a specific height in the gravitational field that depends on the small weight of the fly inside the sphere.

The experiments were discussed online with the students supporting their engagement with additional digital materials and constant supervision.

1 INTRODUCTION

Experiments that have to be performed as a competition are highly motivating for students [1]. The experiment to determine the weight of a fly has to be performed in the home lab based on own experimental concepts. Everything is allowed that the kitchen and the study room provide. The ideas of the students range from self built scales up to changes in the buoyancy of a plastic capsule. Two awards, small book prizes, will be awarded to the best idea and the most precise result determining the weight of an unknown fly (about 30 mg). In addition the natural link between home lab experiments and digital sensors available on the own smartphone gives rise to a

motivating character of the home lab study as naturally any rather simple problem can be solved via a large range of different experimental approaches [2]. In that sense the students realize that a project turns out to have an infinite number of possible solutions involving the sensors and apps available on the smartphone [2].

Digital tools that support data acquisition and analysis as well as further possibilities for information and literature research including teaching videos suitable to explain important aspects of the theory and the configuration of complex experimental setups allow and enable students for self studies necessary to conduct home lab experiments [3, 4].

A pure problem based competition as the suggestion to determine the weight of a fly follows the concept of research-based learning (RBL) with free choice of of the experimental approach which is motivating [1, 5, 6]. Freely chosen learning topics rise motivation and promote interest in sustainability research and environmentally sustainable attitudes and behavior [7, 8].

RBL trains skills such as the ability to independently formulate questions and conceive research plans and to take responsibility for the outcome of projects [8, 9]. RBL is additionally well suited for online support and new technologies as part of blended learning concepts [10, 11, 12, 13, 14]. We experienced results of a competition to determine the weight of a fly in a simple home lab experiment that were rather astonishing and gave a glance how a single home lab experiment can in principle touch many concepts in physics ranging from mechanics to electronics and from statistics to thermodynamics.

2 CONCEPT OF THE EXPERIMENTS

2.1 Example concepts

In principle the most simple approach to measure the weight of a fly is a sensitive scale, however especially that simple approach turns out to be rather complicated because neither sensitivity nor reproducibility can be easily obtained if tools and techniques of precision engineering are missing.

Therefore the students ideas to overcome these limitations are generally focussed on mechanical approaches that use light materials and an easy construction promising the necessary accuracy. Some students indeed have built a pair of scales from straws and/or paper. Even if the mass of the scale itself is small there is a general problem with friction and the observed effect always scales only linearly with the fly mass.

Other students constructed a reversible free swinging pendulum (Kater's pendulum), which consisted of a small piece of wire. The frequency of Kater's pendulum is dependent on the center of mass. The students fixed the fly at different positions on the filament and measured the frequency, however it turned out that again the friction was a serious problem for an accurate measurement.

One approach used a very light car rolling down an incline transferring it's momentum towards a razor blade that was filmed when indicating the maximal

displacement indeed showing the mass of the fly with high accuracy. This approach finally also won the price for the experiment with the best result.

However the project which won the price for the most interesting approach (as judged by a jury) has put the fly into an empty plastics sphere which was swimming on water. Then the students added screw-nuts of known weight and small tablets of artificial sweetener which had a known weight of 60 mg each because a package of 2000 tablets measures 120 g (according to the producers information).

In such way the weight of the plastics sphere could be adjusted until it reached the density of liquid water. The experiment can be conducted in such way, that the sphere still rises slowly in water and suddenly starts to sink just when the fly is added. Then the small weight of the fly leads to a phase transition of the observed dynamics. However the best results were obtained when accurately measuring the kinetics of a sinking sphere with and without the fly and comparing the results with theory. The sphere needs to overcome a fixed distance in a water filled cylindrical tube under gravity. The approach allows for an analytical solution of the problem. The small effect of the weight change of the sphere by adding the mass of a fly (about 0.1 %) is transferred to a macroscopic change of the time needed to sink down.

2.2 The winner project

If a sphere with mass m is accelerated along the z -axis by gravitational force $F_G = mg$ while buoyancy F_A and friction F_{R1} point into the opposite direction (See Fig. 1) the forces calculate as denoted in eq. 1 and define the equation of motion.

Fig. 1. Forces on the sphere in liquid

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F} &= m\ddot{z} = -(\vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_A) + \vec{F}_{R1} \\ \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_A &= (m - m_w)\vec{g} = \Delta m\vec{g} \\ \vec{F}_{R1} &= -6\pi\eta r\dot{z} := \beta\dot{z}\end{aligned}\quad (1).$$

Interestingly the driving force for acceleration of the sphere scales with the difference (Δm) of it's mass and the mass of the displaced water m_w . This difference can be positive (sphere sinks), zero (sphere floats) or negative (sphere rises and swims). When the velocity of the sphere along the z-axis rises the contribution of the laminar (Stokes) friction F_{R1} starts to rise proportionally to the velocity, viscosity of the medium η and the radius of the sphere r following Stoke's law. These values except the dynamical variable z are summarized as a factor β in eq. 1. With this simplification eq. 1 can be rewritten as a simplified linear ordinary inhomogeneous differential equation of 1st order for the velocity of the sphere v (eq. 2).

$$\begin{aligned}m\dot{z} &= -\Delta mg - \beta\dot{z} \\ \dot{z} &= \dot{v} \\ m\dot{v} &= -\Delta mg - \beta v\end{aligned}\quad (2).$$

Eq. 2 is solved by first solving the homogeneous system, variation of the constant and integration of the velocity $v(t)$ to obtain the trajectory $s(t)$:

$$\begin{aligned}v(t) &= \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - 1 \right) + v_0 \\ s(t) &= \frac{-\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(\frac{m}{\beta} e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - \frac{m}{\beta} + t \right) + v_0 t + s_0\end{aligned}\quad (3).$$

If the sphere starts with zero velocity at $z_0 = s_0 = 0$ then the trajectory is driven by the mass difference Δm of the sphere and the displaced water while the inert mass m is much larger. This leads to a very slow movement and a large difference between two trajectories proportional to the mass difference between the sphere and the replaced water mass (see Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Trajectory of two spheres with a mass difference of 75 mg as plotted in Fig. 4

This becomes evident when looking at the theoretical plots of the depth of the sphere when sinking in water at 21°C for a sphere with radius $r=2.1$ cm and a mass of 25 g accelerated by 50 mg mass difference (Fig. 3, right side, black curve) and 25 mg mass difference (Fig. 3, right side, red curve). From these plots it also becomes evident that the approach is more complicated than initially assumed. At the beginning of the experiment the students were focused on the equilibrium condition

$$v(t) = \frac{-\Delta mg}{\beta} \quad (4).$$

Eq. 4 is a general approach to analyse the maximal velocity a free falling object can reach under Stokes friction. However as it can easily be seen from the plot of the velocity in Fig. 3, left side, the equilibrium is reached after more than 150 sec. in a depth of 40 m for a mass difference of 25 mg only and therefore the experimenters can not assume to reach the equilibrium condition under laboratory conditions.

Fig. 3. Theoretical plots of the velocity according to eq. 3 (left side) and its depth when sinking in water at 21°C (right side) for a sphere with radius $r=2.1$ cm and a mass of 25 g when accelerated by 50 mg mass difference (black curve) and 25 mg mass difference (red curve).

3 PROJECT RESULTS

3.1 The weight of the fly

During their first tries the students aimed in determining the mass of the fly by stopping the time the sphere needs to sink down to the ground. However it turned out that their numbers were rather random and did not at all fulfill the achieved precision which was initially expected.

It turned out that the start of the free fall of the sphere was a crucial point and was not easily overcome by just releasing the sphere from the free hand.

So several approaches were tested and improved to gain reproducible initial conditions. One was the fixation of the sphere with a thin filament that was burnt at the moment the experiment was started. Especially when spheres are used which have quite exact the mass of the density of water even the weight of the falling filament and its interaction with the liquid surface tension seems to disturb the measurement. Another approach used a magnet holding the sphere on the ground of the vessel which had slightly less density than water. The sphere was released by quickly removing the magnet. It is also tricky not to disturb the rising sphere in the initial point when the magnet is released.

Fig. 4 shows 2 trajectories of falling spheres after burning the filament in a vessel with only 10 cm of free fall range. As especially the initial point and the first few centimetres of the free fall are the crucial data the students quickly learned that a search for a long tube with long free fall time is quite unnecessary but the repetition of a short free fall and accurate averaging of the results is much more constructive.

Fig. 4. Measurement (black squares) and data fit of two trajectories of falling spheres with a weight difference to the displaced water of 225 mg (left side) and 150 mg (right side)

As seen in Fig. 4 the free falling sphere which was filmed during sinking and the trajectory (black squares in Fig. 4) later evaluated from the movie can be well described by eq. 3 (solid red line in Fig. 4). The fit of the measurement data resulted in a weight of the fly of 75 mg after it had been added to the sphere (Fig. 4, left side) in comparison to the sphere without fly (Fig. 4, right side)

3.2 Fit Curves and statistical errors.

A fit on the measurement data resulted in much better values than just stopping the free fall time. The fit curve shows a much better match with the expected outcome than just a series of stopped time points for the moment when the sphere hits the ground of the vessel. Finally the students determined the weight of the fly to 59 +/- 38 mg which still has somehow a large deviation and needs to be further investigated.

3.3 Systematic deviations

With the possibility to change the weight inside the sphere with small screw-nuts weighting 200 mg and sweetener tablets weighting 60 mg the students additionally could check for possible systematic deviations of their experimental outcome and they could indeed identify a quite long list:

1. It is rather difficult to exactly close the plastic sphere in such way that it perfectly measures the same volume as before. This deviation is the most critical one. Finally the students chose a solid plastic sphere with small interior space that was closed by oiling the surface of the cut and press both halves together.
2. When the water is freshly filled from the tap it does not have 20°C. Therefore the viscosity is not 1 mPas and it deviates strongly as water at 25°C reduces to 0.9 mPas. Therefore the students quickly understood how important it is to control the exact temperature of the water in the vessel.
3. When releasing the sphere still disturbance occurs which might even shortly drag the sphere a little bit upwards. This was especially the case when the students initially used a filament that contracts shortly when heated and turned out to be unsuitable as the curves deviated from the expected results.
4. In water the sphere covered with bubbles that were stuck on the sphere surface and practically led to a virtual increase of the sphere's surface and volume therefore increasing the buoyancy.
5. When not closing the plastic sphere perfectly a drop of water appeared inside and the experiment was completely wrong as the water might be heavier than the fly itself.

The students quantified their systematic deviation finally by a Gaussian error propagation and estimated possible systematic errors of 45 mg which is quite much. When checking with an exact lab scale the fly was determined to only weight 28 mg. However the students were able to separate their statistical errors from systematic errors which is quite helpful for research to understand the role of both, statistical and systematic deviations.

4 CONTINUOUS DIGITAL SUPERVISION

It turned out that quick, regular and flexible supervision of the students via a video conference, both on demand as during a jour fixe, where they shared their experimental results and even presented the procedure on camera was of high value to identify and judge all the errors mentioned and being able to suggest and discuss improvements of the experiments.

Therefore the homelab experiments should always be accompanied by a regular discussion of each experiment. There is not necessarily a need to do such a discussion with each group separately however at least for each experiment with the groups of all students involved.

5 DISCUSSION AND SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPROVEMENTS

During the discussion with the students after they had finished the experiments and presented their results a lot of suggestions had been made how to improve the setup or explore different effects and directions. Some of them are shortly outlined here.

5.1 Mechanical variations of the experiment

The most logical approach is to modify the mechanical setup itself. As mentioned above the release of the sphere was either done by a thin fiber that is burned at the beginning of the experiment or by a magnet that releases the sphere. One could also think how else to construct a “smooth” release and compare the quality of the results. Also the variation of the liquid itself and substitution by oil or other liquids with higher viscosity could be promising to further prolongate the duration of the trajectory. Also a promising approach might be the start of the time measurement at a given height with an initial velocity to get rid of the initial disturbance when the sphere is started and measure just a later part of the curve during the free fall.

5.2 Thermodynamic variations of this experiment

The identification of the strong sensitivity of our results on the water temperature as it changes the viscosity made us think about the influence of further thermodynamic effects on the systematic deviations in our experiment. When considering the opportunity to slow down the process by changing the viscosity of the surrounding medium the students came up with an interesting approach that works with a gradient of the sugar concentration in a cylindrical tube that allows for an equilibrium height in the gravitational field that depends on the small weight of the fly inside the sphere. As the gradient of the sugar concentration can be adjusted infinitesimally one can build a scale where a single mg of weight difference shifts the equilibrium positions by several centimeters. In that sense the sugar gradient scale as shown in Fig. 5 was constructed where the sphere has about 15 cm difference in height when the weight rises by 60 mg.

Fig. 5. Different equilibrium positions of the sphere in dependency on the weight when the sphere falls into a gradient of sugar concentration

Further improvements or different approaches could use a hot air balloon or helium filled balloon which is in a similar equilibrium position in a room's natural air gradient. Such a construction might find its equilibrium positions with meters difference if the weight just changes by few mg.

5.3 Optics and electronics

The best values were obtained when taking a video with subsequent evaluation of the trajectory. However, improved measurements could also track the object optically or at least install photosensors for better and reproducible time measurements. For an accurate determination of the weight in the sugar gradient scale (see Fig. 5) one has to adjust the sugar gradient with high accuracy and also know the local sugar concentration. As the sugar mixes with time, this also needs to be measured continuously and could, for example, be done with refractometry, i.e. the bending of a laser beam when crossing the solution in different height.

6 CONCLUSION

All in all, the students were surprisingly engaged to achieve the best results, which was most probably driven by the competition that was connected with the experiment. From meeting to meeting, the discussed ideas were subsequently investigated by the students, and they started to dig deeper and deeper into the teaching matter. We recognized the importance of continuous digital interaction when doing home-lab experiments. Finally, when we collected the outcome, it was astonishing to understand how deep you can dig into physics with just one single home-lab experiment that is appropriately exploited in all directions and touches all fields of physics.

In that sense, we encourage to motivate students (e.g. by competitions) and ask them to use very simple tools which are available at home and invest the available time into steady discussions of results and further improvements.

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Appendix: Solution of the differential equation of motion for the sphere in liquid

$$\begin{aligned}\vec{F} &= m\ddot{z} = -(\vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_A) + \vec{F}_{R1} \\ \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_A &= (m - m_w)\vec{g} = \Delta m\vec{g} \\ \vec{F}_{R1} &= -6\pi\eta r\dot{z} := \beta\dot{z}\end{aligned}\tag{5}$$

$$\begin{aligned}m\ddot{z} &= -\Delta mg - \beta\dot{z} \\ \ddot{z} &= \dot{v} \\ m\dot{v} &= -\Delta mg - \beta v\end{aligned}\tag{6}$$

Solving the homogeneous system:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{v} &= -\frac{\beta}{m}v \Rightarrow \frac{dv}{v} = -\frac{\beta}{m}dt \\ \Rightarrow \int_{v_0}^{v(t)} \frac{dv}{v} &= \int_0^t -\frac{\beta}{m}dt \\ \Rightarrow \ln\left(\frac{v(t)}{v_0}\right) &= -\frac{\beta}{m}t \\ \Rightarrow v(t) &= v_0 e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t}\end{aligned}\tag{7}$$

Variation of the constant:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v(t) &= c(t)e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} \\
 m\dot{c}(t)e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - \beta c(t)e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} &= -\Delta mg - \beta c(t)e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} \\
 \dot{c}(t) &= \frac{dc(t)}{dt} = \frac{-\Delta m}{m}ge^{\frac{\beta}{m}t} \\
 \int_{c_0}^{c(t)} dc(t) &= \int_0^t \frac{-\Delta m}{m}ge^{\frac{\beta}{m}t} dt = \left[\frac{-\Delta m}{\beta}ge^{\frac{\beta}{m}t} \right]_0^t \\
 \Rightarrow c(t) &= \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta} - \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta}e^{\frac{\beta}{m}t} + c_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

General solution for the velocity (with initial conditions) and integration:

$$\begin{aligned}
 v(t) &= c(t)e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} \\
 c(t) &= 1 - \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta}e^{\frac{\beta}{m}t} + c_0 \\
 \Rightarrow v(t) &= \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - 1 \right) + c_0 e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} + v_0 = \frac{ds}{dt} \\
 c_0 &= 0 \\
 \Rightarrow \int_{s_0}^{s(t)} ds &= \int_0^t \left(\frac{\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - 1 \right) + v_0 \right) dt \\
 \Rightarrow s(t) - s_0 &= \left[-\frac{\Delta mmg}{\beta^2}e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta}t + v_0 t \right]_0^t = \frac{-\Delta mmg}{\beta^2} \left(e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - 1 \right) - \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta}t + v_0 t
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

Solution for $v(t)$ and $s(t)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 v(t) &= \frac{\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - 1 \right) + v_0 \\
 s(t) &= \frac{-\Delta mg}{\beta} \left(\frac{m}{\beta}e^{-\frac{\beta}{m}t} - \frac{m}{\beta} + t \right) + v_0 t + s_0
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$